

THE NEED TO STUDY PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY: IN SEARCH OF MEANING

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses in detail the diversity of forms of human knowledge, as well as the relationship between knowledge and faith. In addition to this, there is an important aspect for the formation of conditions for the professional and personal growth of a specialist. In this article I want to share with you my experience with the little-known test «Homunculus». It seems that everyone has heard of him, but few have seen, and even more so worked with him.

In the beginning, it must be said that pedagogy and psychology are studied together with philosophy, to a large extent systematizing the basic human, psychological and pedagogical knowledge of students on the problems of philosophy, general psychology and pedagogy. Worldview pictures of the world. Components of the worldview and various forms of worldviews. Types and socio-historical types of worldviews. Different pictures of the world. The ratio of knowledge and faith, rational and irrational in human life. Different types of faith. The problem of the relationship between faith and knowledge in various philosophical concepts. The levels of scientific knowledge of objective and subjective reality. Levels of scientific knowledge. Psychological improvement is a condition for the professional and personal growth of a specialist. The study of psychology and pedagogy as a factor in the development of the professionalism of the subject of labor. Acmeological approach to the

problems of human professional development. The qualities of the subject of labor as a specialist. Sources of psychological knowledge. The value of the data of zoo- and comparative psychology for the development of knowledge about the human psyche. The role of the analysis of mental abnormalities for the study of the human mental sphere. Everyday psychological knowledge about oneself and other people. The need for everyday psychological knowledge for the development of psychology. The difference between everyday psychological knowledge and scientific knowledge. The position of a scientific psychologist in relation to everyday psychology. The problem of the reliability of the received psychological information. Dependence of the reliability of the obtained psychological data on the reliability and validity of the methods used. Knowledge is the result of what we have learned, which we can reasonably or factually justify. Knowledge is necessary for a person to orientate himself in

the world around him, to explain and foresee events, to plan and implement activities and to develop others. Knowledge as the main element of the content of general education: knowledge as the main element of the content of general education is the result of knowing the reality of the laws of development of nature, society and thinking. They express the generalized experience of people on, accumulated in the process of social historical practice. Rational and sensory cognition of reality is especially important for psychologists and teachers: that is, through sensations it moves to perception, and through perception into representations through emotions, and again this one rotates in a circle. From the point of view of psychology, sensation is the simplest mental process, consisting in the reflection of individual properties of objects and phenomena of the material world, as well as internal states of the body under the direct influence of stimuli on the corresponding receptors.

Perception is the reflection in the mind of a person of objects or phenomena as a whole, in the aggregate of its properties under the direct influence of objects or phenomena on the sense organs. Representations are images of objects, scenes and events that arise on the basis of their recollection or productive imagination and have a generalized character. Emotions are a mental reflection in the form of a direct biased experience of the vital meaning of phenomena and situations, conditioned by the relation of their objective properties to the needs of a person. Some philosophers and scientists do not include this element as an element of sensory knowledge for reasons that will be discussed later in the section on the relationship between rational and irrational knowledge in human life. The term «knowledge» is usually used in three main meanings.

- Firstly, knowledge means abilities, skills, and abilities that are based on a person's awareness of how to do something, to carry it out. However, from the point of view of psychology, knowing how to do something and being able (to have the skill, ability) to do something are two different things.

- In the second meaning, knowledge is understood as any cognitively significant information, first of all – adequate, correct information. Knowledge is always information, but not all information is knowledge. In the process of processing by a person, information must acquire a symbolic form or be expressed in it with the help of other knowledge stored in memory, it must acquire meaning and meaning. Thus, a number of laws governing the activity of the brain and various mental processes, as well as various rules that include knowledge in the system of social relations, in the cultural context of a certain era, are involved in the transformation of information into knowledge. Thanks to this, knowledge becomes the property of society, and not just of individual individuals. True knowledge, knowledge built on the basis of correct, adequate information, will be called such knowledge that corresponds to its subject, coincides with it.

- Thirdly, knowledge is understood as a special cognitive unit, a special form of a person's relationship to reality, existing alongside and in interconnection with a practical relationship to the world. In the structure of the cognitive process, the result of which is the accumulation and enrichment of knowledge, two types of activity are distinguished: firstly, practical activity in the broadest sense of the word, and secondly, activity specifically aimed at creating knowledge, at producing concepts, that is, theoretical activity as a special type of mental labor. The ratio of knowledge and faith: In a broad sense, faith is knowledge that is accepted

without empirical, rational justification. Faith can be divided into two types: religious and pragmatic. Religious faith is most fully used by theology, in religious philosophical treatises. It is contrasted with empirical and intellectual knowledge and is considered the highest form of human knowledge obtained through divine revelation. Pragmatic faith is a definite scientific hypothesis for which there is no coherent logical and empirical evidence. A specialist who has reached the stage of his maturity and a certain level of development as an individual, personality and subject of social labor, develops on the basis of the harmonious integration of such leading aspects as professional activity, personal development, everyday relations in which the subject of labor productively uses his creative potential and constantly is improving.

For the formation of views, concepts, beliefs, methods are used that have received the general name of methods for the formation of personality consciousness. The methods of this group are also very important for the successful passage of the next important stage of the educational process – the formation of feelings, emotional experience, required behavior. If students are indifferent to pedagogical influence, then, as you know, the process develops slowly and rarely reaches the intended goal. Deep feelings are born when an idea realized by schoolchildren is clothed in bright, exciting images. In the textbooks of previous years, the methods of this group were called shorter and more expressively – methods of persuasion, since their main purpose is to form stable beliefs. It is not knowledge, but beliefs that stimulate the actions of schoolchildren, therefore, not so much concepts and judgments as moral confidence in the social necessity and personal usefulness of a certain type of behavior should be formed at the stage of development of

consciousness. The methods reach the goal when the pupils have developed a willingness to actively participate in the activities provided for by the content of education. The powerful persuasion method is an example.

«There was such a case, we all had teachers, of course, there was one teacher and his student. The student was glorified every day, suddenly the teacher wanted to know who is stronger, and he asked the student by phone:» What do you think, who is stronger than me or you ? «. In response, the student replied:» I. «And then several times he called and got the same answer again. And he did the following, he met him at the beginning of the street, as they lived on the same street. Then the student to this question answered: «You are stronger than me! «, but he did not understand why this is so.» Why do you say that I am stronger, before you said that you are?

«It's simple – he replied – because when you are next to me, then you have no equal, if you are far away, then I have no equal.» Here is the best example for you, in my opinion, after that everyone will treat the teachers more respectfully, since they are also like our second mothers, and they also worry about us, try their best to keep us up to date. Also, for the diagnosis of somatic disorders, a Homunculus test is performed. Before starting the test, a preliminary conversation with the parents is required, a study of the child's medical record. A sheet with a drawing is placed in front of the child and it is proposed to paint it.

To do this, each participant is given the following drawing for painting:

And here it is designed for children of preschool and younger school age. I gave it to them and watched how they paint, how they press the pencil or not After all, we all know that everyone is individual in the world, there are no direct 100% of similar people, well, at least they can find the same solution. Each painted in its own way, there is no uniformity of patterns. Someone pressed, but some did not, someone painted their head red, someone drew eyes after that, we will ask who did you draw? The name of? How many years? What is he doing now, what is he doing at all? Favorite and least favorite pastime? Is he afraid of anything? Where does he live? Who does he live with? Who does he love most of all? With whom is he friends (playing, walking)? What is his mood? His most cherished desire? If he had a choice, how would he defend himself from enemies? What is his health? What and how often does he hurt? What is good, bad about him? Who does he remind you of? Interpretation by A.V. Semenovich of some elements of the «Homunculus» test:

- Buttons, dividing the body in half – gastrointestinal diseases. Curved line of buttons – spinal scoliosis; Buttons to the end – constipation, enuresis, encopresis.
- Colored hands – fine motor skills of hands are not developed.

- Red ears – underdevelopment of phonemic hearing, auditory hallucinations.

- Red hair, finished cap – vegetative-vascular dystonia, hydrocephalus.
- Red mouth – asthma, cough.
- Red wavy lines – vascular disorders.
- Bandage on the throat, beads, collar – inflamed tonsils, situational memories, cord entanglement during pregnancy, thyroid dysfunction, tachycardia.
- Blush on the cheeks – thyroid dysfunction.
- Small mouth, its absence – speech therapy problems.
- Unpainted figure – asomatognosis (non-perception of one's own body).
- The lower part of the body is not painted – enuresis, encopresis.
- Nose – phallus (in combination with red lips and an undeveloped lower part may indicate sexual problems or masturbation). Situationally – watching a porn film the day before.
- Strong pressure on the picture – a sore spot is indicated.
- Spot on the body – hypertonicity of the indicated part of the body.
- The darkened left side – functional disorders of cardiac activity.
- Marked joints – subluxation at birth, joint pain.
- Large strokes of coloring – organic disorders, episynndrome. At the same time, the test determines the presence or absence of such phenomena in the child as hypo / hypertonicity of muscles, rigid bodily attitudes; fluctuations in attention and emotional background when completing the task as a whole and when moving from one painting area to another;

failures of the respiratory rhythm, etc. In diagnostic practice, the test «Homunculus» showed high efficiency (subject to objective interpretation).

Conclusion

However, it should be noted that the performance of this test carries a certain psychoemotional load for the subject. Therefore, it is recommended to choose for a specific study only the necessary thematic questions, selected from the basic questionnaire, or proposed independently. You can return to this image later, having received the necessary additional information. When performing this test, a psychologist should also record both resistance reactions

and emotionally colored statements, which can carry the necessary additional information.

Thus, the Homunculus projective test, modified by us, makes it possible to carry out a voluminous and comprehensive study of the personality, because the questionnaire can include questions of various orientations concerning various spheres of human activity. Moreover, the test can be used for corrective purposes in psychological counseling with clients who have a high level of reflection, as well as in repeated diagnostics in order to analyze the effectiveness of psychological correction, counseling and psychotherapeutic work.

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